

Xifang Helun 西方合論

also known as “Comprehensive Treatise on the West”

By Charles Jones, The Catholic University of America

Entry tags: Pure Land Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions, Religious Group, Text, Chinese Buddhist text, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

The Xifang Helun 西方合論 is a text published in 1599 by Yuan Hongdao 袁宏道 (1568-1610). In it, he exhorts readers to adopt the practices of Pure Land Buddhism, desist from antinomian Chan (Zen) 禪 practices, and engage in moral self-reform. In addition, he answers criticisms of Pure Land Buddhism with reasoned arguments and scriptural citations. Yuan himself was widely known in his own day. Despite his short life, he accomplished almost everything that a member of the literati élite aspired to. He passed the highest levels of the civil service examination at an early age, got a prestigious position in the imperial bureaucracy, gained fame as a poet and literary theorist, and participated in high-level conversations about the intellectual topics of the day, including Chan Buddhism. One of his most influential friends was the iconoclastic Buddhist layman and social critic Li Zhi 李贄 (1527-1602), widely associated with the movement known as “Crazy Chan” (Ch.: kuang chan 狂禪). However, their relationship soured after ten years, and it was partly in response to the antinomian tendencies that Li represented that Yuan composed the Xifang helun. Many of Yuan’s peers looked down upon Pure Land practice as a mere devotional exercise fit only for the peasant classes. Within the ten chapters of this work, Yuan sought to show that Pure Land had wide scriptural support in the most esteemed Buddhist scriptures, that great Buddhist intellectuals of the past such as Nagarjuna had supported it, and that it was consistent with the highest expressions of Buddhist philosophy. He also threw challenges back at Pure Land’s detractors: were they really as enlightened as they claimed? For example, to those who said Pure Land displayed a false dualism between purity and impurity, Yuan caustically asked: if you understand that the two are ultimately the same, can you jump into a latrine and swim around? If not, then maybe you need Pure Land practice. Finally, he advises adherence to all the moral practices of Buddhism such as a vegetarian diet and keeping the Five Lay Precepts. The book was widely popular. Editors of the Jiaxing Buddhist Canon included it, the influential Pure Land monk Ouyi Zhixu 藕益智旭 (1599-1655) included it in his *Jingtu shi yao* 淨土十要 (Ten Essential [Texts] of Pure Land). Decades later, a patron commissioned the painter Chen Hongshou 陳洪綬 (1598-1652) to portray the initial public presentation of the Xifang helun in a painting called *Elegant Gathering* (yaji tu 雅集圖), completed in 1646 or 1647. It remains a classic outlay of Pure Land thought at its most highly-developed stage.

Date Range: 1599 CE - 1599 CE

Region: Beijing-Huguang region

Region tags: China

Places of residence for Yuan Hongdao 袁宏道 (1568-1610) around the time he composed the Xifang Helun 西方合論 in 1599.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yuan Hongdao袁宏道. Xifang helun 西方合論 (“Comprehensive Treatise on the West”), in Taishō Shinshū Daizōkyō 大正新脩大藏經, 100 vols. ed. Takakusu Junjirō 高楠順次郎 et. al. Tokyo: Taishō shinshū daizōkyō issai-kyō kankō kai, 1924. Text no. 1976, vol. 47, p. 385-419.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association (cbeta.org)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: cbeta.org

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

Specify type of paper

- Specify: Do not know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- I don't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Materiality

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Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Do not know

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– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: This book was written using paper and writing brush, and was published using woodblock printing.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: The audience consisted of elite members of the literati or gentry classes who had an interest in Buddhism. Most had passed the highest levels of the civil service examinations. This would amount to a group of several thousand scattered across China.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

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Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Bibliography

Notes: One section of the text organizes Buddhist scriptures by the extent to which they focus on Pure Land teachings and the extensiveness of their presentation of them.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: This book is aimed at Buddhist laymen, not ordained monks or nuns. Thus, it advocates a conventional Confucian morality with a few other specifically Buddhist ethical precepts added.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: This text proposes a concrete rebirth in the "Pure Land" (Ch.: Jingtū 淨土) of the Buddha Amitābha after death. Contemporary Chinese Buddhists preferred to interpret this Buddha and his Pure Land as the purified consciousness of the advanced practitioner rather than as a concrete location.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: Both positions had substantial numbers of followers. Elite Buddhists tended to hold to the position the the Pure Land was a mental state achieved through religious practice. This text seeks to persuade them that the Pure Land is a concrete destination one may access after death.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– I don't know

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: "This world" here means the present world-system, but there are many levels present within it. It encompasses the heavens where gods (both material and immaterial) dwell, titans (Sanskrit: asuras), human beings, animals, hungry ghosts, and hells. The desired goal of the Pure Land is said to be outside of all these levels, and thus rebirth there represents liberation.

↳ In human form?

– Yes

Notes: Given that the human form is one possible rebirth, the answer is really maybe but not necessarily.

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

Notes: Rebirth as an animal is possible, but rebirth as a plant is not.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– No

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha Amitābha brings devotees to his Pure Land after death in response to their practice of reciting his name and/or focusing their minds on him.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other?
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

- ↳ Courage (generic)
– No

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

Notes: As is typical with almost all Mahayana Buddhist texts, this one places a high value on compassion. It advocates vegetarianism and an active program of assistance to all living beings.

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes

Notes: Generosity is one of the Six Perfections in Mahayana Buddhism, and this text recommends it.

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– No
- ↳ Cooperation
– No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes

- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No
- ↳ Other important virtues
– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Apologetic

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: Those reborn in the Pure Land have the "divine eye" and the "divine ear," allowing them to see and hear throughout the cosmos.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?
– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?
– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?
–Specify: No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?
– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

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Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

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– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

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Beliefs

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↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

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↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

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Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

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– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

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↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

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↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

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↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

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– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

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Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text guide divination practices?

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha Amitābha brings devotees to his Pure Land after death in response to their practice of reciting his name and/or focusing their minds on him.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: This book is aimed at Buddhist laymen, not ordained monks or nuns. Thus, it advocates a conventional Confucian morality with a few other specifically Buddhist ethical precepts added.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: As is typical with almost all Mahayana Buddhist texts, this one places a high value on compassion. It advocates vegetarianism and an active program of assistance to all living beings.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: Generosity is one of the Six Perfections in Mahayana Buddhism, and this text recommends it.

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– No

↳ Strength (physical)
– No

↳ Power/status/nobility
– No

↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No

↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– I don't know

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– I don't know

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

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Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?
– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?
– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?
– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?
– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?
– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?
– No

Does the text mention warfare?
– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:
– Other

Does the text specify forms of taxation?
– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?
– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?
– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– I don't know

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– I don't know

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– I don't know

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– I don't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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